

Comparative analysis of different atmospheric Weather condition in free space optical Communication system

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Abstract: Free space optical (FSO) communication is one of the recent technologies in a mode of wireless communications. FSO is a data transmission method that requires a line-of-sight between transmitter and receiver from unguided media through an optical carrier in the atmosphere. In the FSO communication system attenuation of information mainly arises because of atmospheric turbulence such as scattering, absorption, scintillation, and fluctuation in the intensity of laser beam, etc. Here in this paper, we are comparing the attenuation coefficient in different atmospheric condition for FSO system. Atmospheric attenuation models are discussed in detail. At the end advantages and application are also highlighted.

Keywords: *Atmospheric turbulence, free space optical (FSO), lasers, LOS (line-of-sight), optical wireless communication (OWC), and scintillation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Free space optical (FSO) communication is the latest technology, which uses LASER beam to transmit the data wirelessly through propagation of light in unguided medium. FSO gives line-of-sight communication because transmitted bandwidth is narrow and operating spectrum is IR and visible. FSO also known as wireless optical communication (WOC) which links point-to-point connectivity. WOC is categorized into two major parts-indoor and outdoor. Infrared communication without physical connection is referred to as indoor WOC and outdoor WOC is the one which uses invisible infrared light for communication which is based on line-of-sight technology.

Thousands of years ago various form of optical communication was used for transmission of data. For the

long-distance communication, sunlight was used for signal transmission. Later on, ancient Greeks and Roman shaped this technology [1]. In 1810, Carl Friedrich Gauss invented a technology in which controlled beam of sunlight was directed to cell station by using couple of mirrors. The former technology known as Heliograph also called as wireless solar telegraphy [1].

In 1880, photo phone technology was developed by the Alexander Graham bell, and his assistant Charles Sumner Trainer [2]. On 3 June 1880, bell invented a new discovery, which is the world's first wireless transmission of the signals between a distance 700feet. US military communication use this technique firstly. Nowadays LASER or LED is used as a source in the optical wireless communication (WOC) system. Laser transmission was first used in 1960. The scientist got first successful transmission of signal through ruby laser at a distance of 25 miles [3], but due some to demerit of laser beam caused high divergence of the signal and because of atmospheric effect on the signal, cop ability was less and attenuation induced was 1000db/km. In 1970s, low loss optical fiber was introduced which was great success in the communication field and attenuation level was 20db/km.

Now, free space optical communication (FSO) has gained immense interest due to advancements, such as high data rate with low power consumption, easy installation, and it is license free spectrum. FSO system transmit the IR signal which requires line-of-sight condition, but some factor such as atmospheric turbulence, multipath fading, scattering, absorption degrade the performance of FSO system. The performance of the system can be determined on the basis of

bit error rate (BER), signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and quality factor (Q-factor) at the receiving end. BER factor, and intensity of the signal are mainly affected by atmospheric attenuation in which BER larger, as the attenuation increases. [3]. Relationship between FSO system and BER is inversely proportional.

II. FREE SPACE OPTICAL (FSO)

COMMUNICATIONS SYSTEM MODELLING

The FSO communication system encompass mainly three section- transmitter, channel (free space), and receiver. Sub section of transmitter are- source, divider, modulator, laser diode, optical amplifier (if necessary). Transmitter section transmit the information in the form of data, then encodes the information with the help of pseudo-random bit sequence (PRBS) resultant pulse is binary. This binary pulse is fed it into NRZ divider section. NRZ encoding procedure signified by two individual binary bits '0' and '1' have been used. NRZ output acts as input of the Mach-Zehnder. [8]. Two input port in Mach-Zehnder modulator are- electrical port, and optical port. When the output of laser and input of Mach-Zehnder optical port are connected to each other, resultant signal is optical.

Figure 1: Block diagram of FSO communication system

Optical signal carries forward to next section which is optical amplifier. Optical amplifier is use to enhance the strength of signal. Optical signal is sent to atmospheric channel. At the receiver, received the optical signal is recovered back into electrical form with help of PIN photo diode or Avalanche photo detector. This electrical signal sent to low pass filter (LPF) which removes the unwanted

high frequency, noise, and interference from the signal. In output of LPF acts as input of demodulator which converts the signal back to the original form. BER analysis is used for evaluation at receiver end [10].

III. MODULATION

Selection of modulation takes place on the basis of two criteria; power efficiency and bandwidth efficiency. Maximum data rate with low BER belongs to power efficiency and bandwidth efficiency evaluates extreme information for given bandwidth with precise modulation. FSO system operates on a number of modulation scheme such as binary, and multilevel. Generally binary format is used because of its ease and greater power efficiency. Normally, intensity modulation is used in FSO communication system. FSO uses OOK modulation deployed with IM technique. [1]. Mechanism of OOK is ON/OOF keying which is generated form of amplitude phase shift key (ASK). In OOK modulation technique, transmit '1' to turn optical signal source 'ON', and transmit '0' to turn the optical signal is 'OOF'. This phenomenon known as non-return to zero (NRZ). Return to zero (RZ) is another method in which digital bit '1' come back to 0 position. RZ is highly efficient than NRZ and PPM refers to binary modulation scheme PPM, on other hand used in bottomless space communication and Large efficient spectrum.

IV. APPLICATION AND ADVANTAGES OF FSO

FSO communication system has an enormous advantage. Such as-

1. This system provides large bandwidth to carry the information up to several km with high speed. As known to all carrier frequency increase with increase information carrying capacity. Transmission rate up to 10Gbps is already launched.
2. Very less time required for installation of system. And
3. also reinstall is possible without any complications.

4. This system has License free spectrum but another network requires license. [5]. the system uses frequency above 300GHz which does not require license.
5. High security provided by this system because of line-of-sight condition i.e., system highly direction narrow beam delivers then signal not infiltrate with wall thus system do not outflow the information.
6. Low power consumption (~1/2 of RF). [26].

Today user get access to the optical system because of the growth in the system performance. Due to huge advantages of the system, it has a large range of application. Some of application are described below-

1. **Monitoring and video investigation:** FSO technology presents a powerful support for the high quality of video transmission. Every commercial and industrial area uses surveillance camera for monitoring and wireless video camera are uses for the public safety and including military purpose.
2. **Enterprise/organization connectivity:** Today, FSO system provides connectivity to all over the world. This system is also used in inter-schools/organization in the form of LAN-TO-LAN connectivity without network traffic. This system can work as a bridge to the number of buildings. Easily communicates inter organization with high bandwidth and speed.
3. **Broadcasting:** In broadcasting, FSO plays as an important role in live shows, news, and reality shows telecast. Signal from the camera is required to be sent to the broadcast medium which associated to the central office through satellite. Now days of FSO signal is widely use in every communication links such as (HDTV) high-definition television.
4. **Disaster recovery:** In emergency situation like natural disasters, terrorist attacks, etc. flexible and high bandwidth system are needed [8]. FSO system immediately inform to headquarter or main office so that they can take quick action promptly.

V. DEMERITS

Due to huge advantages system enhance the performance, but there is some disappoint factor which affect the signal. Some of them are-

1. **Absorption:** In the terrestrial atmosphere, water (H₂O) and oxygen (O₂) are present. The optical signal gets absorbed in these molecules and gets deviated. [11]. thus, optical beam power density is decreased. Absorption occurs during day time by the reflection of sunlight and earth radiometric temperature.
2. **Atmospheric Turbulence:** Variation in the Atmosphere and environment causes signal disturbance. Air and wind particles are mixed top each other with different temperature which degrades the performance of atmospheric channel. [6]. Refractive index of air varies according to fluctuation in the air density.
3. **Atmospheric Attenuation:** In a different atmospheric weather condition, generally fog, haze, etc. signal gets affected which is known as atmospheric turbulence. All the atmospheric attenuation is depending on wavelength, but it is not always correct. Haze condition is depended on wavelength. Attenuation in 850nm is larger than the 1550 nm wavelength. In Foggy weather condition, attenuation does not depend on wavelength.
4. **Scattering:** Scattering phenomena occurs when incoming optical beam collides with atmosphere particles like dust particles, etc. which deviates the direction of optical signal. Long distance beam is transmitted, reduction in intensity of the signal due directional rearrangement. [9]. Types of scattering which causes the atmospheric Attenuation-
 - a. **Rayleigh scattering-** In atmosphere various gases and aerosol are present which attenuates of the incoming light. When colliding particle size is small and wavelength is large then this type of scattering.is induced

- b. **Mie scattering-** The lower level of atmosphere contains pollen, dust, and other particle which scatter the signal over the FSO system. This type of scattering is known as Mie scattering. It is wavelength dependent. When colliding particle size is equal to wavelength then this type of scattering induced.
- c. **Non selective scattering-** This type of scattering occurs in lower level of atmosphere from the earth surface. It is also called as geometric scattering. When colliding particle size is larger than wavelength, then non selective scattering induced.
5. **Scintillation:** The variation in the intensity of light is known as atmosphere scintillation. Temperature variation also causes scintillation. Heat releases from the earth surface or through man-made devices which distorts the signal and disturbs the line-of-sight. Scintillation also cause varied BER, and largely mitigates the performance of signal. The intensity of signal fluctuates.

VI. ATTENUATION DUE TO ATMOSHERIC WEATHER CONDITION

FSO communication system transmits the signal in atmosphere that is free space. Due to changes in atmospheric conditions, signal gets attenuated. In different atmospheric weather conditions such as haze, rain, fog, snow, transmission of the optical beam, mitigates the performance of the FSO system and visibility of the communication link is very less.

a. **Calculation atmospheric attenuation:**

Most of the factor affecting by the signal, atmospheric attenuation is the one of them. [7]. the optical signal deviates because of atmospheric attenuation and can be related with the help of Beer-Lambert law:

$$P_R = P_T \exp(-\alpha z)$$

Where, P_R received power, P_T transmitted power, α shows atmospheric attenuation, and z is related distance in km. Evaluation of optical signal attenuation can be computed with Kim and Cruse model.

Kruse model-

$$q = \begin{cases} 1.3 & \text{if } V > 50 \text{ km} \\ 1.6 & \text{if } 6 < V < 50 \text{ km} \\ 0.58 V^{1/3} & \text{if } V < 6 \text{ km} \end{cases}$$

Kim model-

$$q = \begin{cases} 1.6 & \text{if } V > 50 \text{ km} \\ 1.3 & \text{if } 6 < V < 50 \text{ km} \\ 0.16V + 0.34 & \text{if } 1 < V < 6 \text{ km} \\ V - 0.5 & \text{if } 0.5 < V < 1 \text{ km} \\ \{ 0 & \text{if } V < 0.5 \text{ km} \end{cases}$$

a. **Rain:**

During rainfall condition transmission of laser beam fluctuates the signal. If the light beam strikes with water droplet it causes scattering of optical beam and does not recover the full information at the receiving end. If the water droplets are denser, it causes high attenuation while less attenuation occurred in light rainfall condition. Visibility of FSO system is decided on the basis of rainfall quantity and also based on [7] absorption, and reflection of light during rainfall time. In nonselective scattering attenuation is not depend on the wavelength. [6].

b. **Fog:**

One of the major challenges in FSO is fog which attenuates the signal up to hundreds of decibel/km. Absorption, scattering of the optical signal occurs due to presence of fog atmospheric condition. Fog density changes according to size of particles and height from the earth surface. In dense fog condition, it is difficult to maintain communication link while in light fog condition system performance increase with the increasing transmission power. The BER is dense fog and light fog is 10^{-3} /km and 10^{-3} in 200 km respectively. Most of the factor affecting by the signal, atmospheric attenuation is the one of them. [7].

c. **Snow:**

Large diameter of snow particle as compared to rain drop, highly attenuates the signal. Light blocks due to

snowflakes. When snowflakes collide with photons it scatters the signal. Attenuation occurred due to snow.

d. Cloud:

An essential portion of earth's atmosphere is cloud but it is main hindrance for the optical beam. The cloud formation is deposition of water vapours above the earth's surface, it accumulates and creates the cloud. As the optical beam is transmitted from earth's surface to the atmosphere, clouds fully block the signal. Thus, it is difficult to calculate the attenuation caused by clouds.

VII. BER PROBABILITY

The performance criteria of FSO communication system are decided on the basis of BER parameter. Fluctuation in signal intensity determine through BER at the receiving end. The optical BER extend i.e., 10^{-8} to 10^{-12} has been gotten at the lessening scope of 28.1–28.5 dB at 40 Mbps. As the constriction increments to greatest degree of 35 dB, the BER arrives at the immersed degree of 8.2×10^{-1} . At information pace of 35 Mbps, the optical BER extend is accomplished somewhere in the range of 26 and 27 dB constriction, 22 and 23.5 dB lessening for 30 Mbps, 20 and 21.5 dB weakening for 25 Mbps.[8].

Table 1: Attenuation in different conditions

S. No.	Weather condition (nm)	wavelength	Attenuation dB/km
1	Heavy rain	1550(nm)	188.48
	Moderate fog		256.48
	Fog		201.05
	Snow		467.00
	Clear weather		178.00
2	Heavy rain	1310(nm)	190.07
	Moderate fog		257.90
	Fog / Snow		204.00
	Clear weather		180.30
3	Heavy rain	850(nm)	198.00
	Moderate fog		261.82
	Fog / Snow		473.09
	Clear weather		184.52

It is noted that comparative analysis of different atmospheric weather condition with different operating

wavelength which shows attenuation coefficient increase as the density of weather condition is increase. As shown in table very clear or drizzle/clear weather less attenuation but in fog, rain has large attenuation coefficient. 1550nm wave length is much better proficiency rather than other wave length. Interruption free transmits the optical signal in very clear weather in 1550 wave length.

VIII. GENERATION OF OPTICAL NETWORK

The headway in the semiconductor business and fibre optics prompted the advancement of rapid optical communication system dependent on fibre optic frameworks. Optical network as seen a significant advancement from first to fifth era. Right now, size and intricacy of the system have been radically incremented. This development of web information is because of assortment of the internet providers, for example, video conferencing, distributed computing, 3D pictures and portable access with video customers. So as to provide these administrations, optical system is filling in as an earlier system because of its enormous range accessibility. In earlier Optical system utilizes Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) method. In this method individual light source is modulated with respective wavelength are assigned to the multiplexer and send it to optical fibre. At the receiving end optical signal get separated out with the help of de-multiplexer.

In WDM, a fixed wavelength (i.e., data transfer capacity) is allocated to the client even if the transmission capacity required is less, it causes spectrum/data transmission wastage. Notwithstanding wasteful range usage, WDM arrange design unfit to satisfy future system difficulties of centre system, for example, Quality of Services (QOS), transfer speed request versatility, vitality utilization [1] and so on. The network service provider had a challenge to increase the network, as earlier one. Consequently, elastic optical network (EON) phenomena have been proposed. Elastic optical system is based on the concept of

optical orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (O-OFDM). [12-13]. EON's permit Slicing of Spectrum alluded, as by using EON's the bandwidth allocation granularity can be reduced down to 12.5GHz or less. Therefore, elastic optical networks (EONs) built with O-OFDM can realize more agile bandwidth management than the wavelength-division multiplexing. It overlaps the same wavelength source of data the, achieve high spectrum efficiency. Advantage of O-OFDM is maximum like hood decoding, low inter-symbol-interference (ISI), no wastage of spectrum.

IX. FUNDAMENTALS PRINCIPLE OF FSO

FSO-connects through the troposphere are essentially impacted by climate conditions. Along these lines, some important characteristics of the air must be talked about before portraying the optical remote frameworks in more detail. The most minimal piece of the air up to 10 km over the Earth's surface is known as the troposphere or the climate circle. As increase the height from the earth surface, refractive index changes. Ordinarily the refraction record decline with the tallness, yet at climate reversal circumstances there is be alternate relationship [23].

Barometric conditions debase laser correspondences through the environment in two, different ways. To start with, the environment goes about as a variable attenuator between the transmitting and getting terminals. Second, a free space laser interface is exposed to scintillation.[13]. Due to different atmospheric condition, it get attenuates the signal along the transmission path. Normally, during mist day's higher attenuation of the signal in the atmosphere while during clear days attenuates the signal. Downpour doesn't impact optical transmissions intensely, on the grounds that raindrops have the size of a couple of millimetres and are enormous contrasted with laser wavelengths (1.5 microns) and along these lines cause negligible dissipating of the laser vitality. Besides, water has negligible retention at a 1550 nm laser wavelength.

Therefore, transmission of the signal through optical fibre during the rainy season is not cause higher attenuates of signal strength. (Around 3 dB/km).

X. PREVIOUS WORK

In this review [17] Free-space optical correspondence frameworks have gotten huge consideration from specialists lately. Right now, audit past work on alleviating scintillation impacts of barometrical choppiness on Free Space Optical correspondence frameworks. Procedures explored include: levelling in semiconductor optical speaker, spatial and transient assorted variety, opening averaging, and coding schemes. We talk about different free space optical correspondence framework and channel models, hand-off helped frameworks and far-field assumptions.

In this paper [19]."Free Space Optical Communication: A Review": With the overall interest for bigger data transmission and more prominent portability there is a fast headway of broadband remote correspondences. The high limit and low loss of optical fibre has seen its outrageous development over the most recent couple of decades in the LAN's and WAN's. Free space optical (FSO) remote correspondence has developed as a reasonable innovation for overcoming any issues in existing high data rate fibre arrange and as a brief spine for quickly development versatile remote correspondence foundation. Free space optical correspondence offers the possibility to send enormous measure of information security over moderate separations without the cost of laying fibre optic link. The innovation is useful where the physical association of the transmitter and collector areas is difficult.

XI. CONCLUSIONS

FSO has enormous advantages like high bandwidth, low cost, etc., due to these merits, the conventional communication system is switched to optical technology. Since the attenuation of signal in FSO is highly affected by atmospheric turbulence, here we have highlighted the

various performance parameter associate with the different modulation techniques. Signal get highly attenuated in snow weather condition as compared to rain. Attenuation is least at 1550 nm. Different technique is present to enhance the performance of the FSO communication system such as EON, equalization in semiconductor. EON reduce the blocking of the signal and also mitigates wastage of spectrum and transmission of signal with high data rate.

References

- [1]. Khaligi and M. Uysal, "Survey on free space optical Communication: A communication theory perspective," IEEE Communication. Surveys and Tutorials, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 2231-2258, June (2014).
- [2]. H. kaushal, G. kaddoum, "Optical Communication in Space: Challenges and Mitigation Techniques", IEEE pub., Volume: PP, Issue:991553- 877X, August (2016).
- A. A. Huurdeman, the Worldwide History of Telecommunications. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley-Inter science, 2003.
- [3]. J. Hecht, "Laser evolution," SPIE Professional Magazine. [Online].
- [4]. Available: <http://spie.org/x34446.xml>.
- [5]. V. W. S. Chan, "Free-space optical communications," J. Light w. Technol. vol. 24, no. 12, pp. 4750-4762, Dec. 2006.
- [6]. H. A. Fadhil, A. Amphawan, H. A. B. Shamsuddin et al. "Optimization of free space optics parameters: an optimum Solution for bad weather conditions," Optik, vol. 124, no. 19, pp. 3969-3973, 2013.
- [7]. Mehatab Singh, Simran Arora and Rajveer, "Performance Comparison between PIN and APD Photodiodes for use in Free Space Optical Communication Link," IJIRAE, vol. 2, issue 8, August 2015.
- [8]. D. Ananddkuma, R.G Sangeetha." Emulation of free space optical link in weak atmospheric turbulence" microwave and optical technology 2018.
- [9]. <http://www.laseroptronics.com/index.cfm/id/57-66.htm>.
- [10]. Md Mehedi Farhad, Md. Rubaiyat Islam, Nazmun Nahar Islam, Maruf Mohammad Ali, "Performance Analysis of Turbo Coded Free Space Optical Communication System over AWGN Channel", International Journal of Science and Advanced Technology (ISSN 2221-8386) Volume 3, No 7, July 2013.
- [11]. J. Singh and N. Kumar, "Performance analysis of Different Modulation format on free space optical communication System, Optik, vol. 124, no. 20, pp. 4651-4654, 2013.
- [12]. F. U. Rashid, S. K. Semakuwa, "Performance Analysis of Free Space Optical Communication Under the Effect of Rain in Arusha Region, Tanzania," International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology, vol. 3, Issue 9, September 2014.
- [13]. J. Kaufmann, "Free space optical communications: an overview of Applications and technologies," in Proceedings of the Boston IEEE Communications Society Meeting, 2011.
- [14]. L. C. Andrews, R. L. Phillips, and C. Y. Hopen, "Laser beam Scintillation with applications", SPIE Press, 2001.
- [15]. John Schuster, Free Space Optics (FSO) Technology Overview, Chief Technology Officer, Tera beam Corporation.
- [16]. F. David, "Scintillation loss in free-space optic systems", LASER2004, Vol. 5338. San Jose USA, 2004.
- [17]. Factors affecting FSO -International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT) vol. 3, Issue 11, May 2014.
- [18]. Chairs of WG3 Erich Leitgeb Gorazd Kandus Zabih Ghassemlooy, Properties and Types of FSO -Final Report of WG3 of COSTIC0802: Channel modelling for free-space optical systems and airborne Terminals. December 2012 Final update: May 2013.

- [19]. Srikant patnaik, Srusti Srujanika sahu, Anshuman Panda, Chandni Jaiswal, "Free Space Optical Communication: IRJET impact factor Value 2016.
- [20]. M. Ijaz, Z. Ghassemlooy, J. Pesek, O. Fiser, H. Le Minh, and E. Bentley, "Modeling of fog and smoke attenuation in free space optical Communications link under controlled laboratory conditions," Journal of Light wave Technology, vol. 31, no. 11, Article ID 6497447, pp. 1720–1726, 2013.
- [21]. F. Yang, J. Cheng, T. Tsiftsis, "Free-space optical communication with Nonzero bore sight pointing errors," IEEE Trans. Commun. 62(2), 713– 725 (2014).
- [22]. Z. Ghassemlooy, W. Popoola, and S. Rajbhandari, Optical Wireless Communications: System and Channel Modelling with MATLAB, New York: CRC Press, 2013.
- [23]. Li Y, Mehdi I, Maestrini A, Lin RH, Papapolymerou J. A Broadband 900-GHz Silicon micromachined two-anode frequency Tripler. IEEE Trans Microw Theory Tech. 2011; 59:1673–1681.
- [24]. Li Y, Mehdi I, Maestrini A, Lin RH, Papapolymerou J. A Broadband900-GHz Silicon micromachined two-anode frequency Tripler. IEEE Trans Microw Theory Tech. 2011; 59:1673–1681.
- [25]. Siles JV, Maestrini A, Alderman B, et al. A single-waveguidein-phase Power-combined frequency doubler at 190 GHz. IEEE Microw Compon Lett. 2011; 21(6):332–334.
- [26]. Vaishali, S. Senchet "performance analysis of atmospheric condition Over terrestrial free- space optical communication" Springer 2018.
- [27]. V. W. S. Chan, "Free-space optical communications," J. Light wave Tech., vol. 24, no. 12, pp. 4750–4762, 2006.